

Characteristic Study of Manufacturing Output and Global Commerce

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Abstract

Every nation's economy is significantly impacted by international trade. It makes it possible to meet the requirements of the populace and promotes the nation's internal growth. The exchange of commodities and services between nations is known as international trade. The study examines developments of specialization in industrial production and global commerce from 1980 to 2013. In order to determine whether these patterns are consistent with the three different strands of trade theories—the traditional Heckscher-Ohlin theory, the "new" trade theories based on increasing returns to scale, and the economic geography theories based on vertical linkages between industries—it looks into whether specialization has increased in international trade. I discover that there is evidence of growing specialization in global trade, and that there is some evidence to support each of the three strands of tradetheories.

Keywords Specialization, Trade Theories, Economic Geography, and International Trade.

Introduction

A descriptive statistical assessment of industrial production and trade patterns during the reference period is given in this section. Simple statistical methods like average shares and annual growth rates serve as the foundation for the investigation. The entire time is subdivided as follows for brevity: 1980–1990 was Period I; 1991–2000 was Period II; 2001–2007 was Period III; and 2008–2013 was Period IV. The first phase includes the 1980s import deregulation and first liberalization period. The extensive liberalization regime of the 1990s began during the second period. The third phase includes additional trade liberalization up until the 2008 external demand shock brought on by the world economic crisis. Period IV describes a setting with significant demand shock and external uncertainty brought on by the start of the global financial crisis.

The actual value added increase of India's manufacturing production at the sectoral level, calculated at 2004–05 prices, is shown in the table. The corresponding sectoral shares in total manufacturing for a specific time period are shown in figures in parenthesis. The average annual growth rate of organized industrial production during the whole period (from 1980 to 2013) is approximately 8%. During the 1980s (period I), manufacturing production increased at this rate; but, during the 1990s (period II), it fell to 6% annually. Nonetheless, production showed significant improvement in the subsequent period, with a double-digit growth rate of 15% annually between 2007–08. After that, the growth rate fell to what was seen in the 1990s.

Aim of study

The aim of study this paper is Characteristic Study of Manufacturing Output and Global Commerce.

**Review of
Literature**

For this paper many books, research papers, newspapers and online websites has been reviewed and mentioned in the complete paper.

Main Text

Trend of manufacturing sector(1980-2013)%per annum